

The effect of 6-substituent on isomerization of tetrazolo[1,5-*a*]pyridines and conformational analysis of 2-azidopyridines : A DFT study

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Abstract : The phenomenon of ring-chain isomerism and conformation are important aspects of chemistry. The effect of substituents CH₃, OH, Cl, OH, CN and NO₂ at the 6-position of tetrazolo[1,5-*a*]pyridines, on the ring opening of tetrazole to *cis*-2-azidopyridines were studied using Density Functional Theory (DFT). The results indicated that the tetrazole form is largely favored with CH₃ and OH substituents compounds while the other substituents -Cl, CN and NO₂ shift the equilibrium toward azide isomer. The B3LYP/6-311G** level of theory employed to investigate. The process of conversion of *cis*-2-azidopyridines to the *trans*-2-azidopyridines. The lower rotational barrier of the azido group in the *cis* ↔ *trans* isomerization and the significant increase of the dipole moment of tetrazole isomer are determining factor in ring opening tautomerism. The low values of the energies of the transition states favor cyclization. For all substituents, the DFT calculations revealed that the *cis*-form of 2-azidopyridines is more stable than *trans*-form.

Keywords : Ring opening, tautomerism, *cis-trans* transformation, barrier of rotation, DFT, tetrazole-azide equilibrium.

Introduction

Heterocyclic azides are known to spontaneously cyclize to give the fused tetrazole form or more generally exist as an equilibrium mixture. This has been described variously in the literature as a tautomerism, as an azidomethane-tetrazole (imideamide-tetrazole) equilibrium, as a 1,5-dipolarcyclization and as valence isomerization^{1,2}.

A variety of heterocyclic groups like tetrazolopyridines, tetrazolopyridazines, trazolopyrimidines, tetrazoloazines, tetrazolopurines etc. have been reported to exhibit the tetrazole ↔ azide isomerization³. The two forms i.e. the tetrazole and azide, have contrasting chemical properties. The tetrazole ring is electronegative while the azido is electropositive. The tetrazole-azide isomerization is governed by the electron donating capacity of the heterocycle to which the tetrazole ring is fused. Thus, electron withdrawing groups favor the azide and vice versa electron donating groups stabilize the tetrazole structure. There are a few reports⁴⁻⁶ on tetrazole-azide equilibrium in tetrazolo[1,5-*a*]pyridines (Fig. 1). The experimental works on tetrazole-azide equilibrium in the 6-position on

tetrazolo[1,5-*a*]pyridines sit that 6-NO₂, 6-COOH and 6-Cl favor the tetrazole forms.

There is a report on the effect of substitution on the tetrazole-azide equilibrium in tetrazolo[1,5-*a*]pyridines at which the -CH₃ as substituent in 5-position favor tetrazole form, while any substituent favor azide form⁷. We were investigated in systematically examining the effect of substitution at the 6-position on tetrazole-azide equilibrium. The 6-position being nearest to the reaction center (the dissociating N3-N4 bond) could be expected to dramatically modulate the equilibrium reaction via an electronic and steric effect. We have examined theoretically the influence of various substituents (R = H, CH₃, OH, CN, NO and Cl) at the 6-position in tetrazolo[1,5-*a*]pyridines (Fig. 1) on the stabilities of the tetrazole and azide isomers and on the barrier of transformation of *cis* to *trans* for 2-azidopyridine resulting from ring opening of tetrazolo[1,5-*a*]pyridine by using Density Functional Theory (DFT) with B3LYP/6-311G** level. The equilibrium geometry parameters, total energy and thermodynamic parameters were calculated.

Fig. 1. Isomerization and conformation of tetrazolo[1,5-a]pyridine.

Method of calculations :

All calculations were performed with GAMESS⁸ program package. The hybrid DFT method based on Becke's three functional⁹ with non-local correlation provide by the Lee, Yang and Parr functional (LYP)¹⁰ is used with 6-311G**¹⁹ basis set level. The effect of electron correlation on geometry optimization are taken into account intensively by using Beck's three-parameter-hybrid (B3LYP) method²⁰⁻²² in the Density Functional Theory with 6-311G** basis set. The B3LYP method provides energetic typically better than Hatree-Fock method²³ and can reproduce better geometrical parameters comparable to the experimental values than any other method²⁴. In addition, the B3LYP results are closer to correlated post Hatree-Fock approximations such as the MP2 method or better^{25,26}. In all cases the minimum energy or transition state nature of the stationary points was verified from frequency analysis. The geometry of ground state, transition state and products of the studied molecules with C1 symmetry were fully optimized. The ring opening reaction of tetrazole being with the molecule in it's geometry optimized ground state and is simulated by stepwise elongation of r(N3-N4) the bond (Fig. 1). The nature of stationary point is characterized by calculating the corresponding vibrational frequency and transition states are located and confirmed by having one imaginary frequency of vibration.

Results and discussion

Ring opening of tetrazole :

Tetrazolo[1,5-a]pyridine : The geometric parameters, energies and charges are given in Table 1 of tetrazolo[1,5-a]pyridines. The thermodynamic parameters for tetrazole,

transition state and azide are given in Table 2. The equilibrium geometric structure for tetrazole, transition state and azide are given in Fig. 2.

The results in Table 1 calculated at B3LYP/6-311G** showed that the two isomers of the azidopyridine are close in energies. The relative energy between the two isomers is 1.767 kcal/mol only. A significant result is the confirmation that the tetrazole is a much stronger dipole, 6.189D than open isomer, 2-azidopyridine, 2.938D.

The apparent polarity of the tetrazolo-isomer leads to a highly negative value for ΔH for solvation, in polar solvents and leads to the formation of the tetrazole than the azide isomer¹¹, ΔH is -4.759 kcal/mol. The energy barrier of the isomer process is 18.269 kcal/mol, which supports tetrazole \leftrightarrow azide conversion. This process (tetrazole \leftrightarrow azide) conversion based on elongation of r(N3-N4) bond. This conclusion is confirmed by results given in Table 1. The calculated N3-N4 bond length of 1.359 Å in tetrazole form compared with experimental value 1.33 Å¹². The bond distances of the ring lie between the corresponding C-N and N-N single and double bond distances, which indicates that all the tetrazole rings are aromatic. As the tetrazole \leftrightarrow azide reaction proceeds, elongation of bond length N3-N4 imposes a strain on the molecule, and the total energy increases until a transition state is reached at r(N3-N4) = 1.999 Å. The position of this transition state is confirmed by having one imaginary frequency $\nu = 359.74$ cm⁻¹. In this transition state the C9-N1 bond elongates to 1.394 Å, while the N1-N2 bond shortens to 1.306 Å and N2-N3 bond shortens to 1.173 Å, also the N1N2N3 angle increases to 132.851° as shown in Table 1. The N4-C9 bond distance shortens to 1.328 Å and begins has some double bond characters and the

Table 1. Total energy, dipole moment and equilibrium geometrical parameters, bond length (Å), bond order, bond angles (°) and charges for tetrazolo[1,5-*a*]pyridine (R = H) calculated at B3LYP/6-311G** level of theory

Parameter	Tetrazole	TS(1)	<i>cis</i> -2-azido	TS(2)	<i>trans</i> -2-azido
<i>E</i> (au)	-411.9859206	-411.9568059	-411.9887365	-411.9758281	-411.9825027
Dipole moment (D)	6.189	4.063	2.738	3.723	3.213
Bond length (bond order)					
N3-N4	1.359 (1.077)[15,16,18]	1.999 (0.397)	-	-	-
N2-N3	1.299 (1.423)[15,16,18]	1.173 (1.927)	1.128 (2.214)[18]	1.133 (2.182)	1.133 (2.164)
N1-N2	1.344 (1.291)[15,16,18]	1.306 (1.297)	1.239 (1.316)[18]	1.231 (1.365)	1.233 (1.300)
C9-N1	1.332 (1.435)[15,16,18]	1.394 (1.186)	1.412 (1.029)[18]	1.440 (0.961)	1.419 (1.077)
N4-C9	1.376 (1.024)[15,17,18]	1.328 (1.275)	1.331 (1.469)[18]	1.326 (1.534)	1.329 (1.506)
N4-C5	1.368 (1.081)[15,17,18]	1.340 (1.361)	1.337 (1.483)[18]	1.338 (1.467)	1.334 (1.488)
C8-C9	1.414 (1.224)[15,17,18]	1.410 (1.282)	1.400 (1.343)[18]	1.397 (1.345)	1.403 (1.291)
Bond angle (°)					
C9N4N3	108.227[15,16]	95.351	-	-	-
N2N3N4	105.367[15,16]	90.353	-	-	-
N1N2N3	112.983[15,16]	132.852	172.649[18]	172.618	172.448
Charge density					
N4	-0.373	-0.460	-0.361	-0.295	-0.314
N3	-0.051	0.008	-0.125	-0.167	-0.144
N2	-0.075	0.064	0.312	0.265	0.277
N1	-0.285	-0.312	-0.336	-0.263	-0.265
C9	0.454	0.454	0.331	0.229	0.265
Imaginary frequency (I)	-	359.74	-	91.53	-

[15,16,18]; are the crystallographic data and X-ray diffraction experiments.

Table 2. Thermodynamic parameters of the tetrazole-azide process of tetrazolo[1,5-*a*]pyridines and shading cells [] for *cis-trans* conversion of 2-azidopyridines calculated at B3LYP/6-311G** level of theory

Substituents	Er	dH	dE	dE*	dS
H	-1.767 [3.912]	-4.759 [4.186]	18.269 [8.100]	13.882 [9.217]	5.255 [-0.402]
CH ₃	-0.463 [3.866]	-3.812 [4.176]	18.988 [8.058]	14.312 [9.149]	5.616 [-0.432]
OH	-10.778 [1.564]	-13.063 [1.782]	16.043 [6.052]	11.683 [6.949]	4.998 [-0.306]
Cl	-8.457 [3.159]	-11.525 [4.144]	14.406 [8.297]	10.047 [9.403]	5.321 [-0.312]
NO ₂	-13.326 [4.132]	-15.918 [4.410]	10.976 [8.665]	7.015 [9.794]	4.896 [-0.194]
CN	-6.333 [4.149]	-9.313 [4.448]	14.424 [8.591]	10.276 [9.695]	5.323 [-0.348]

Er : Reaction energy is given by $E_{\text{product}} - E_{\text{reactant}}$ dH : Heat of reaction is given by $Er + d(\text{ZPE}) + d(\text{TC})$.dE : Energy barrier is given by $E_{\text{TS}} - E_{\text{ST}}$.dE* : Activation energy is given by $dE + d(\text{ZPE}) + d(\text{TC}) + RT$.

dS : Enthalpy of reaction.

C9N4N3 bond angle decreases to 95.3°. A further increase in r(N3-N4) bond leads to the conversion of tetrazolo[1,5-*a*]pyridine to corresponding *cis*-2-azidopyridine. Elongation of r(N3-N4) bond is accompanied by shifting of C9-N1 to 1.412 Å, which becomes has single bond character, and N1-N2 shifted to shorter value 1.239 Å, which becomes has double bond character. The bond angle N1N2N3 shifted to higher value 172.648° which corresponds with free azide group. The charges at N4 and N3 at tetrazole are -0.373 and -0.0513 respectively while, in case of azide the charges are changed to -0.361 and -0.125 on the same nitrogen atoms (N4, N3).

*6-Cl, OH and CH₃ tetrazolo[1,5-*a*]pyridine* : The values obtained for equilibrium bond length, bond angle, charge density, bond order, total energies and dipole moment for all the studied structures are given in Tables 3 to 7. The elongation of r(N3-N4) from 1.363 to 1.926 Å at transition state which, confirmed by having one imaginary frequency ($\nu = 383.23 \text{ cm}^{-1}$). For the open ring structure of *cis*-form of 5-chloro-2-azidopyridine, the value

Fig. 2. Equilibrium geometry of reactant, transition states, intermediates and product in the conversion of tetrazolo[1,5-*a*]pyridine to *cis*-2-azidopyridine followed by rotation to *trans*-2-azidopyridine using B3LYP/6-311G** level theory.

Table 3. Total energy, dipole moment and equilibrium geometrical parameters, bond length (Å), bond order (σ), bond angles ($^\circ$) and charges for 6-chlorotetrazolo[1,5-*a*]pyridine calculated at B3LYP/6-311G** level of theory

Parameter	Tetrazole	TS(1)	<i>cis</i> -2-azido	TS(2)	<i>trans</i> -2-azido
E (au)	-871.6003556	-871.577398	-871.6138321	-871.6006103	-871.6076819
Dipole moment (D)	6.023	4.026	3.937	4.003	3.744
Bond length (bond order)					
N3-N4	1.363 (1.080)[15,16,18]	1.926 (0.439)	-	-	-
N2-N3	1.297 (1.421)[15,16,18]	1.180 (1.885)	1.127 (2.219)[18]	1.132 (2.188)	1.132 (2.171)
N1-N2	1.342 (1.289)[15,16,18]	1.312 (1.284)	1.241 (1.303)[18]	1.232 (1.354)	1.235 (1.291)
C9-N1	1.331 (1.435)[15,16,18]	1.384 (1.216)	1.407 (1.044)[18]	1.434 (0.973)	1.414 (1.090)
N4-C9	1.381 (1.001)[15,17,18]	1.335 (1.226)	1.336 (1.431)[18]	1.330 (1.495)	1.333 (1.470)
N4-C5	1.370 (1.060)[15,17,18]	1.331 (1.359)	1.318 (1.527)[18]	1.317 (1.500)	1.314 (1.532)
C8-C9	1.411 (1.232)[15,17,18]	1.408 (1.284)	1.398 (1.353)[18]	1.394 (1.361)	1.400 (1.301)
Bond angle ($^\circ$)					
C9N4N3	108.145[15,16]	96.658	-	-	-
N2N3N4	105.219[15,16]	92.329	-	-	-
N1N2N3	113.219[15,16]	130.500	172.532[18]	172.443	172.297
Charge density					
N4	-0.402	-0.475	-0.348	-0.279	-0.299
N3	-0.032	0.027	-0.112	-0.157	-0.133
N2	-0.068	0.065	0.312	0.267	0.278
N1	-0.279	-0.307	-0.333	-0.261	-0.261
C9	0.459	0.470	0.338	0.233	0.268
Imaginary frequency (I)	-	383.23	-	90.96	-

[15,16,18]; are the crystallographic data and X-ray diffraction experiments.

of C9-N1 bond length shifted to longer value 1.426 Å and the N1-N2 compressed to 1.248 Å, also the bond angle N1N2N3 shifted to 172.532° which corresponding with azide formation. The values of charges at N4 and N3 at tetrazole are -0.402 and -0.032 respectively while in case of *cis*-form of 5-chloro-2-azidopyridine the charges are -0.348 and -0.112, respectively. Thermodynamic parameters indicates that the energy barrier of the tetrazole \leftrightarrow azide reaction is 14.406 kcal/mol, lower than that for parent molecule, so rate of isomerization reaction in case of 6-Cl faster than parent compound (R = H) and the reaction is exothermic. The dipole moment shifted from 6.023D in tetrazole to 3.336 in *cis*-form.

In case of hydroxyl group, the elongation of $r(\text{N3-N4})$ from 1.369 Å in tetrazole to 1.943 Å at transition state which detected by presence of only one imaginary frequency ($\nu = 367.42 \text{ cm}^{-1}$). The tetrazole, transition state and *cis*-form of 5-hydroxy-2-azidopyridine are graphically represented in Fig. 4. A significant result is the confirmation that the tetrazole is a much stronger dipole than open isomer, 2-azidopyridine. The apparent polarity

of the tetrazolo-isomer leads to a highly negative value for ΔH , which is agree with previous study¹¹. Hydroxyl group increases the charges on N4 and N3 compared to parent compound. Tetrazole is more polar (7.54D) than *cis*-2-azidopyridine (1.544D). Thermodynamic parameters are given in Table 2 indicates that the value of enthalpy is more negative -13.063 kcal/mol so, the reaction is exothermic.

The values of the equilibrium geometrical parameters, energies, dipole moment and charges are given in Table 5. The both of the two isomers of methyl substituent are exist in the same time where, the relative energy between the two isomers (azidopyridine-tetrazole) is only 0.46 kcal/mol. The transition state is formed at $r(\text{N3-N4})$ is 2.017 Å which detected by presence of only one imaginary frequency ($\nu = 345.56 \text{ cm}^{-1}$), tetrazole, transition state and azide are graphically represented in Fig. 5. For the product azide the bond angle N1N2N3 shifted to 172.747° corresponding with free azide.

Charges at N4 and N3 at tetrazole are -0.437 and -0.056 while, in *cis*-form of 5-methyl-2-azidopyridine the

Fig. 3. Equilibrium geometry of reactant, transition states, intermediates and product in the conversion of 6-chlorotetrazolo[1,5-*a*]pyridine to *cis*-form of 5-chloro-2-azidopyridine followed by rotation to *trans*-form of 5-chloro-2-azidopyridine calculated at B3LYP/6-311G** level of theory.

Table 4. Total energy, dipole moment and equilibrium geometrical parameters, bond length (Å), bond order (σ), bond angles ($^\circ$) and charges for 6-methyltetrazolo[1,5-*a*]pyridine (R = CH₃) calculated at B3LYP/6-311G** level of theory

Parameter	Tetrazole	TS(1)	<i>cis</i> -2-azido	TS(2)	<i>trans</i> -2-azido
<i>E</i> (au)	-457.227573	-487.20458777	-487.2447488	-487.2351043	-487.24225596
Dipole moment (D)	7.503	5.483	1.545	2.229	1.709
Bond length (bond order)					
N3-N4	1.369 (1.055)[15,16,18]	1.943 (0.426)	-	-	-
N2-N3	1.294 (1.432)[15,16,18]	1.179 (1.891)	1.129 (2.205)[18]	1.132 (2.184)	1.132 (2.169)
N1-N2	1.345 (1.277)[15,16,18]	1.310 (1.287)	1.239 (1.317)[18]	1.231 (1.361)	1.234 (1.304)
C9-N1	1.331 (1.443)[15,16,18]	1.388 (1.206)	1.411 (1.033)[18]	1.437 (0.964)	1.417 (1.080)
N4-C9	1.380 (1.020)[15,17,18]	1.333 (1.244)	1.336 (1.442)[18]	1.331 (1.505)	1.333 (1.486)
N4-C5	1.369 (1.059)[15,17,18]	1.335 (1.344)	1.328 (1.444)[18]	1.328 (1.423)	1.325 (1.438)
C8-C9	1.412 (1.235)[15,17,18]	1.406 (1.294)	1.394 (1.376)[18]	1.390 (1.382)	1.397 (1.321)
Bond angle ($^\circ$)					
C9N4N3	108.335[15,16]	96.589	-	-	-
N2N3N4	104.969[15,16]	91.753	-	-	-
N1N2N3	113.357[15,16]	131.092	172.799[18]	172.533	172.429
Charge density					
N4	-0.423	-0.496	-0.434	-0.369	-0.389
N3	-0.039	0.019	-0.130	-0.166	-0.139
N2	-0.071	0.055	0.309	0.267	0.278
N1	-0.288	-0.312	-0.332	-0.267	-0.269
C9	0.457	0.465	0.334	0.229	0.266
Imaginary frequency (I)	-	367.42	-	92.92	-

[15,16,18]; are the crystallographic data and X-ray diffraction experiments.

charges are changed to -0.398 and -0.189 respectively. Tetrazole is more polar, dipole moment is 6.2D while *cis*-2-azidopyridine less polar, dipole moment is 2.8D. Thermodynamic parameters are given in Table 2, the value of energy barrier is 18.988 kcal/mol so, the rate of tetrazole-azide tautomerism in case of CH₃ slower than parent compound. The value of enthalpy is more negative -3.812 kcal/mol so, the reaction is exothermic.

6-Nitro and chloro-tetrazolo[1,5-*a*]pyridine :

Table 6, the total energy of tetrazole -616.522H compared to -616.542H of azidopyridine. A difference is 3.33 kcal/mol between two isomers with the azidopyridine of lower energy. There is no difference in polarity between two isomers, so *cis*-form of 5-nitro-2-azidopyridine is more stable than 6-nitrotetrazole. The elongation of r(N3-N4) till 1.873 Å a transition state is formed and detected by presence of only one imaginary frequency ($\nu = 408.85 \text{ cm}^{-1}$). Further increase in r(N3-N4) till opening the tetrazole ring and produce *cis*-6-nitro-2-azidopyridine with bond angle N1N2N3 172.41°. The

structures of tetrazole, transition state and azide are shown in Fig. 6. The values of charge on N4 and N3 in tetrazole are -0.449 and -0.009, in azidopyridine are -0.344 and -0.097. From thermodynamic parameters in Table 2, the value of energy barrier is 10.976 kcal/mol so, the rate of tetrazole-azide tautomerism in case of NO₂ faster than other compounds. The value of enthalpy is more negative -15.918 kcal/mol so, the reaction is exothermic. Table 7, the total energy of tetrazole -504.239H compared to -504.249H of azidopyridine. A difference is 6.33 kcal/mol between two isomers with the azidopyridine of lower energy. There is no difference in polarity between two isomers, so *cis*-form of 5-cyano-2-azidopyridine is more stable than 6-cyanotetrazole. The elongation of r(N3-N4) till 1.939 Å a transition state is formed and detected by presence of only one imaginary frequency ($\nu = 384.23 \text{ cm}^{-1}$). Further increase in r(N3-N4) till opening the tetrazole ring and produce *cis*-form of 5-cyano-2-azidopyridine with bond angle N1N2N3 172.47°. The structure of tetrazole, transition state and azide are shown

Fig. 4. Equilibrium geometry of reactant, transition states, intermediates and product in the conversion of 6-hydroxytetrazolo[1,5-*a*]pyridine to *cis*-form of 5-hydroxy-2-azidopyridine followed by rotation to *trans*-form of 5-hydroxy-2-azidopyridine calculated at B3LYP/6-311G** level of theory.

Fig. 5. Equilibrium geometry of reactant, transition states, intermediates and product in the conversion of 6-methyltetrazolo[1,5-*a*]pyridine to *cis*-form of 5-methyl-2-azidopyridine followed by rotation to *trans*-form of 5-methyl-2-azidopyridine calculated at B3LYP/6-311G** level of theory.

Table 5. Total energy, dipole moment and equilibrium geometrical parameters, bond length (Å), bond order (), bond angles (°) and charges for 6-methyltetrazolo[1,5-*a*]pyridine (R = CH₃) calculated at B3LYP/6-311G** level of theory

Parameter	Tetrazole	TS(1)	<i>cis</i> -2-azido	TS(2)	<i>trans</i> -2-azido
<i>E</i> (au)	-451.3200904	-451.28983097	-451.3208285	-451.30798699	-451.3146671
Dipole moment (D)	6.187	4.097	2.836	3.619	3.064
Bond length (bond order)					
N3-N4	1.361 (1.108)[15,16,18]	2.017 (0.390)	-	-	-
N2-N3	1.299 (1.410)[15,16,18]	1.173 (1.928)	1.128 (2.212)[18]	1.133 (2.181)	1.133 (2.164)
N1-N2	1.342 (1.295)[15,16,18]	1.304 (1.304)	1.239 (1.318)[18]	1.230 (1.368)	1.233 (1.304)
C9-N1	1.333 (1.432)[15,16,18]	1.397 (1.173)	1.414 (1.023)[18]	1.441 (0.954)	1.421 (1.071)
N4-C9	1.376 (1.028)[15,17,18]	1.326 (1.298)	1.329 (1.489)[18]	1.323 (1.558)	1.327 (1.530)
N4-C5	1.376 (1.050)[15,17,18]	1.346 (1.335)	1.342 (1.441)[18]	1.343 (1.416)	1.340 (1.439)
C8-C9	1.412 (1.230)[15,17,18]	1.408 (1.286)	1.399 (1.337)[18]	1.396 (1.339)	1.402 (1.284)
Bond angle (°)					
C9N4N3	108.096[15,16]	95.185	-	-	-
N2N3N4	105.453[15,16]	89.775	-	-	-
N1N2N3	112.919[15,16]	133.443	172.748[18]	172.674	172.478
Charge density					
N4	-0.437	-0.502	-0.398	-0.328	-0.349
N3	-0.056	-0.002	-0.129	-0.171	-0.147
N2	-0.074	0.068	0.312	0.264	0.276
N1	-0.286	-0.316	-0.341	-0.268	-0.270
C9	0.456	0.458	0.340	0.237	0.272
Imaginary frequency (I)	-	345.56	-	86.84	-

[15,16,18]; are the crystallographic data and X-ray diffraction experiments.

Fig. 6. Equilibrium geometry of reactant, transition states, intermediates and product in the conversion of 6-nitrotetrazolo[1,5-*a*]pyridine to *cis*-form of 5-nitro-2-azidopyridine followed by rotation to *trans*-form of 5-nitro-2-azidopyridine calculated at B3LYP/6-311G** level of theory.

Table 6. Total energy, dipole moment and equilibrium geometrical parameters, bond length (Å), bond order (), bond angles (°) and charges for 6-nitrotetrazolo[1,5-*a*]pyridine (R = NO₂) calculated at B3LYP/6-311G** level of theory

Parameter	Tetrazole	TS(1)	<i>cis</i> -2-azido	TS(2)	<i>trans</i> -2-azido
<i>E</i> (au)	-616.52108397	-616.50359286	-616.54231967	-616.52851155	-616.5357346
Dipole moment (D)	6.522	5.077	5.559	5.558	5.625
Bond length (bond order)					
N3-N4	1.366 (1.085)[15,16,18]	1.873 (0.486)	-	-	-
N2-N3	1.297 (1.414)[15,16,18]	1.186 (1.849)	1.126 (2.227)[18]	1.131 (2.191)	1.131 (2.174)
N1-N2	1.341 (1.284)[15,16,18]	1.320 (1.257)	1.244 (1.291)[18]	1.233 (1.346)	1.236 (1.282)
C9-N1	1.327 (1.443)[15,16,18]	1.373 (1.261)	1.404 (1.057)[18]	1.430 (0.982)	1.410 (1.100)
N4-C9	1.384 (1.020)[15,17,18]	1.336 (1.233)	1.331 (1.451)[18]	1.326 (1.515)	1.329 (1.490)
N4-C5	1.372 (1.017)[15,17,18]	1.336 (1.300)	1.317 (1.546)[18]	1.316 (1.529)	1.313 (1.550)
C8-C9	1.412 (1.230)[15,17,18]	1.415 (1.250)	1.404 (1.319)[18]	1.399 (1.328)	1.406 (1.267)
Bond angle (°)					
C9N4N3	107.753[15,16]	97.171	-	-	-
N2N3N4	105.246[15,16]	94.056	-	-	-
N1N2N3	113.364[15,16]	128.431	172.406[18]	172.361	172.136
Charge density					
N4	-0.449[18]	-0.512	-0.344[18]	-0.274	-0.294
N3	-0.009[18]	0.049	-0.097[18]	-0.147	-0.124
N2	-0.059[18]	0.053	0.312[18]	0.267	0.277
N1	-0.270[18]	-0.303	-0.334[18]	-0.260	-0.257
C9	0.443[18]	0.459	0.331[18]	0.227	0.262
Imaginary frequency (I)	-	408.85	-	90.25	-

[15,16,18]; are the crystallographic data and X-ray diffraction experiments.

in Fig. 7. The values of charge on N4 and N3 in tetrazole are -0.457 and -0.024, in azidopyridine are -0.377 and -0.103. From thermodynamic parameters in Table 2, the value of energy barrier is 14.424 kcal/mol so, the rate of tetrazole-azide tautomerism in case of CN is faster than parent compound. The value of enthalpy is more negative -9.313 kcal/mol so, the reaction is exothermic.

Rotation barrier of azide group for the cis-trans transformation :

The ring opening of tetrazolo[1,5-*a*]pyridine produces *cis*-conformer of 2-azidopyridine, this structure has another conformer *trans*-conformer of 2-azidopyridine, so after conversion of tetrazolo[1,5-*a*]pyridine to *cis*-2-azidopyridine it is accompanied by transformation to *trans*-2-azidopyridine as shown in Fig. 1. The rotation barrier of the above transformation has been calculated at B3LYP/6-311G** level of theory. The azide group is rotated around the C9-N1 single bond by varying the dihedral angle N2N1C9N4, θ . By specified amounts, freezing at each specific dihedral angle and allowing geometry optimi-

zation for all other parameters. The dihedral angle N2N1C9N4 is changed from 0°, *cis*-form to 180°, *trans*-form. At each change the total energy is calculated. A state of maximum energy was obtained at a rotational angle $\theta = 90^\circ$ where by a saddle point analysis is applied to get the optimized parameters of transition state. Hessian analysis is applied to confirm the presence of the transition state through vibrational analysis. Thermodynamic parameters of rotation process for all studied compounds are given in Table 2. The variation of the energy with the angle of rotation is given in Figs. 2-7.

The transition state of rotation of azide group is produced at $\theta = 100.02^\circ$, with rotation barrier of 8.1 kcal/mol compared to 6.753 kcal/mol in previous study¹³. The results in Table 2 indicated that the relative energy between *cis* and *trans* is 3.912 kcal/mol. The *cis*-2-azidopyridine is more stable than *trans*-2-azidopyridine. The optimized structures of *cis*-, transition state and *trans*-forms are shown in Fig. 2.

In case of *cis*-conformer of 5-chloro-2-azidopyridine,

Table 7. Total energy, dipole moment and equilibrium geometrical parameters, bond length (Å), bond order (), bond angles (°) and charges for 6-cyanotetrazolo[1,5-*a*]pyridine (R = CN) calculated at B3LYP/6-311G** level of theory

Parameter	Tetrazole	TS(1)	<i>cis</i> -2-azido	TS(2)	<i>trans</i> -2-azido
<i>E</i> (au)	-504.23935795	-504.21379198	-504.24945048	-504.2357594	-504.24283802
Dipole moment (D)	6.820	5.085	5.188	5.624	5.634
Bond length (bond order)					
N3-N4	1.356 (1.111)[15,16,18]	1.939 (0.439)	-	-	-
N2-N3	1.300 (1.412)[15,16,18]	1.178 (1.904)	1.126 (2.224)[18]	1.131 (2.190)	1.131 (2.172)
N1-N2	1.342 (1.293)[15,16,18]	1.314 (1.275)	1.243 (1.298)[18]	1.233 (1.351)	1.236 (1.286)
C9-N1	1.330 (1.436)[15,16,18]	1.382 (1.223)	1.406 (1.045)[18]	1.433 (0.971)	1.413 (1.092)
N4-C9	1.377 (1.023)[15,17,18]	1.329 (1.260)	1.328 (1.475)[18]	1.323 (1.541)	1.327 (1.512)
N4-C5	1.379 (1.014)[15,17,18]	1.349 (1.307)	1.341 (1.463)[18]	1.341 (1.444)	1.338 (1.468)
C8-C9	1.413 (1.222)[15,17,18]	1.414 (1.254)	1.404 (1.314)[18]	1.400 (1.319)	1.406 (1.263)
Bond angle (°)					
C9N4N3	108.346[15,16]	96.293	-	-	-
N2N3N4	105.319[15,16]	92.047	-	-	-
N1N2N3	112.936[15,16]	130.736	172.471[18]	172.432	172.79
Charge density					
N4	-0.457	-0.515	-0.377	-0.305	-0.326
N3	-0.024	0.036	-0.103	-0.151	-0.127
N2	-0.062	0.062	0.312	0.264	0.276
N1	-0.274	-0.310	-0.341	-0.266	-0.264
C9	0.455	0.474	0.355	0.252	0.287
Imaginary frequency (l)	-	384.23	-	92.3	-

[15,16,18]; are the crystallographic data and X-ray diffraction experiments

Fig. 7. Equilibrium geometry of reactant, transition states, intermediates and product in the conversion of 6-cyanotetrazolo[1,5-*a*]pyridine to *cis*-form of 5-cyano-2-azidopyridine followed by rotation to *trans*-form of 5-cyano-2-azidopyridine calculated at B3LYP/6-311G** level of theory.

the transition state is formed at $\theta = 100.018^\circ$, with rotation barrier of 8.297 kcal/mol. However Cl substituent decreases the difference energy (3.859 kcal/mol) between the two isomers (*cis* and *trans*) but *cis*-form is more stable between. The graphical structure for *cis*, transition state and *trans* are shown in Fig. 3. In case of 5-hydroxy-2-azidopyridine the transition state is formed at $\theta = 89.724^\circ$, with rotation barrier of 6.052 kcal/mol. The optimized geometric parameters of transition state are given in Table 4. The relative energy between the *cis* and *trans* decreases

with hydroxyl group. *cis* form is more stable than *trans* by 1.564 kcal/mol. Hydroxyl group reduce the negative charge on N4 which reduced the repulsion forces with other nitrogen atoms. Cl and OH groups have induced effect.

In case of strong withdrawing groups (i.e. NO₂ and CN), the transition state is formed at $\theta = 100.101^\circ$, with rotation barrier of 8.665 kcal/mol in case of NO₂ group. The relative energy between the *cis* and *trans* is 4.132 kcal/mol. This result showed that the same order of *cis*

Fig. 8. Variation of rotational energy as well as dipole moment with rotation angle for the transformation of *cis*-conformer to *trans*-conformer.

and *trans* of the other groups (OH, Cl). *cis*-form is more stable than *trans*-form. For CN as substituent, the transition state is formed at $\theta = 100.119^\circ$, with rotation barrier of 8.591 kcal/mol. The optimized geometric parameters of transition state are given in Table 7. The *cis*-form is more stable than *trans*-form by 4.149 kcal/mol. The variation of rotational energy as well as dipole moment with rotation angle for the transformation of *cis*-conformer to *trans*-conformer of 2-azidopyridine for all substituents are shown in Fig. 8. In using methyl group as substituent, the transition state is formed at $\theta = 99.765^\circ$, with rotation barrier of 8.058 kcal/mol. The optimized geometric parameters of transition state are given in Table 5. A difference is 3.866 kcal/mol between two isomers with the *cis*-conformer of 5-methyl-2-azidopyridine of lower energy.

Conclusion :

In the present work, DFT (B3LYP) combined with the basis set 6-311G** used to study the tetrazole-azide equilibrium in tetrazolo[1,5-*a*]pyridine and study the effect of substitution (R = H, Cl, OH, CH₃, NO₂ and CN) in position number 6 on ring opening of tetrazolopyridines to *cis*-2-azidopyridines. The produced *cis*-conformer of 2-azidopyridines have another conformer *trans*-conformer of 2-azidopyridines, so study the effect of substituents on rotation of azide group in conversion of *cis* \leftrightarrow *trans* process. A methyl group at the 6-position, hydroxyl group and parent compound are seen to favor the tetrazole form more than *cis*-conformer of 2-azidopyridine. The stability of closed form of tetrazole for these compounds attributed to;

- (i) The distribution of charge density on *cis*-conformer of 2-azidopyridines shows a built up of charge density on N4 and N3 atoms, once they come at distance ring closure takes place.
- (ii) Tautomerization of tetrazoles to *cis*-conformer of 2-azidopyridines isomer start by elongation of N3-N4 bond which requires a change of hybridization of atomic orbitals on N8 from sp^2 to sp , this step requires energy but the formation of the *cis*-conformer of 2-azidopyridines isomer leads to a lower dipolar species, the dipole moment of tetrazoles greater than 6D whereas that of the *cis*-conformer of 2-azidopyridines \approx 2D. The large

dipole moment values leads to a large stability of tetrazole form in R = H, OH and CH₃.

While any group having an electronegative atom i.e. R = NO₂, Cl and CN directly attached to the 6-position, stabilizes the *cis*-conformer of 2-azidopyridine isomer. These functional groups that stabilize the azide, decrease the activation energy of transition state for isomerization, also decrease value of energy barrier and vice-versa. From parameters of thermodynamics the rate of ring opening fast for 6-NO₂ and slow in 6-CH₃. The height of the rotation barrier of the transformation of *cis*-conformer of 2-azidopyridine to *trans*-conformer of 2-azidopyridine is relatively small 6.052 kcal/mol for 6-OH and varied from 8.1–8.665 kcal/mol for parent compound and 6-NO₂, which mean that the rotation process takes place easily with decreasing rate in case of R = NO₂ and CN. The energy of *cis*-form lower than *trans*-form of 2-azidopyridine for all the studied compounds and there is no difference in polarity between two isomers, so all these substituents favor *cis*-form.

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